

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE MANIFESTATION OF SELF-ACTUALIZATION AT DIFFERENT AGE PERIODS**Kurbonboyev Azimbek Nazirboy ugli**National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan named after Nizami,
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Annotation. This article extensively highlights the significance of self-actualization characteristics in individuals at different age stages, as well as the psychological views of foreign scholars and the essential aspects of self-actualization throughout life and activity. Furthermore, the paper presents a quantitative and qualitative analysis of a study conducted within the framework of examining differences in the manifestation of self-actualization levels among individuals of different ages.

Basic concepts: self-actualization of personality, personal activity, early adolescence, adolescence, maturity, aspiration for creativity, autonomy, cognitive needs, aut sympathy.

Аннотация. В данной статье широко освещается значение особенностей самоактуализации личности в различные возрастные периоды, психологические взгляды зарубежных учёных, а также важные аспекты самоактуализации в процессе жизни и деятельности. Кроме того, представлен количественный и качественный анализ результатов исследования, проведённого в рамках изучения различий в проявлении уровня самоактуализации у лиц разного возраста.

Ключевые слова: самоактуализация личности, активность личности, ранняя юность, юность, зрелость, стремление к творчеству, автономность, познавательные потребности, ауто симпатия.

Introduction. The main problem posed in our research is to determine the level of self-actualization in individuals of different age groups. Based on this goal, the structural structures of self-actualization in individuals of early adolescence, adolescence and adulthood were studied. Influencing factors are studied. In particular, one of the main tasks of our research is to determine which structural components of self-actualization are dominant in individuals of different age groups, to study their different aspects and to analyze them.

Review of relevant literature. The term “self-actualization” was first introduced as a scientific category by K. Goldstein (1939). Based on his theory of cognitive rehabilitation, he proposed considering symptoms in the context of the patient's personality. He explained a number of changes in the behavior of patients with brain injuries with the concepts of “self-actualization” and “self-expression”. According to K. Goldstein, “self-actualization” represents the body's ability to rebuild itself under the influence of injury” [1]. He noted that self-actualization is the only and main motive of the body, which serves as a basis for self-realization, development, self-improvement of the whole organism, and the creative aspirations of the individual.

According to Maslow, self-actualization is the process of becoming the person one wants and can be. Self-actualization is the full realization of one's talents and abilities; it is the unfolding of one's hidden creative potential; every person has talents and abilities [2].

Research methodology. As is known, in order to scientifically study the nature of self-actualization in individuals of different age groups, the methodology of N.F.Kalina (“Diagnostics of the level of self-actualization of an individual”) was selected. This methodology is aimed at examining the level of manifestation of such important components of self-

actualization in individuals of early adolescence, adolescence and adulthood as time planning, values, view of human nature, cognitive needs, striving for creativity, autonomy, spontaneity, self-awareness, autosympathy, communication, and flexibility in communication.

Analysis and Results. This methodology was conducted on a selected group of subjects, and the results were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Expression of differences in self-actualization in individuals of different age groups (N=462)

(By Kruskal-Wallis H-test)

Components	Age periods	N	Rank averages	H	p		
Targeting time	Early adolescence	9	16	200.03	7	21,59 01	p≤0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	230.33			
	Maturity	6	14	269.10			
Values	Early adolescence	9	16	193.78	5	23,52 01	p≤0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	264.11			
	Maturity	6	14	242.33			
A look at human nature	Early adolescence	9	16	211.04	5	13,21 01	p≤0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	223.38			
	Maturity	6	14	263.35			
Knowledge needs	Early adolescence	9	16	209.34	7,918	5	p≤0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	239.24			
	Maturity	6	14	249.35			
Striving for creativity	Early adolescence	9	16	207.35	5	13,40 01	p≤0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	261.76			
	Maturity	6	14	228.99			
Autonomy	Early adolescence	9	16	235.76	1,501	5	p>0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	220.52			
	Maturity	6	14	237.62			

Spontaneity	Early adolescence	9	16	237.00	2,115	5	p>0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	238.25			
	Maturity	6	14	218.34			
Self-awareness	Early adolescence	9	16	226.64	7,813	5	p≤0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	219.21			
	Maturity	6	14	249.50			
Autosympathy	Early adolescence	9	16	232.62	0.338	5	p>0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	235.20			
	Maturity	6	14	226.47			
Establishing connection	Early adolescence	9	16	234.01	0,203	5	p>0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	227.55			
	Maturity	6	14	232.57			
Flexibility communication	Early adolescence	9	16	231.01	0.272	5	p>0.0
	Adolescence	7	14	227.81			
	Maturity	6	14	235.78			

According to Tab.1, when the time-targeting component of self-actualization, which is manifested among individuals in early adolescence, adolescence, and adulthood, was studied, significant differences were noted in this regard ($H=21.597$; $p\leq 0.001$). It is clear from this that the tendency for a person to focus on the present moment, to leave his life for “later” and not to try to live from the past or future, is more developed in individuals in early adolescence and adulthood than in adolescents. This manifestation of the results may be due to the fact that in early adolescence and adolescence, individuals have a lot of things planned for the future and are unable to properly distribute their time. This is a serious obstacle for adolescents of this age to pay close attention to the essence of the events that are happening to them at the moment.

When comparing the indicators of individuals of different age groups in terms of the manifestation of the values component, significant differences were found between them. ($H=23.525$; $p\leq 0.001$). Based on these indicators, it is worth noting that the value sphere of people of different ages differs from each other, and the analysis of factors that are considered valuable for themselves, the focus on values that are important for their future life and activities, and other similar situations are more often observed among adolescents than among individuals in early adolescence and adulthood. Such a manifestation of differences can be explained by the fact that the level of understanding of the values necessary for life in early adolescence is lower

than in subsequent stages of ontogenesis, and in adulthood, as a result of the full understanding of the value sphere, the main emphasis on it weakens.

The results of individuals in early adolescence, adolescence, and adulthood on the manifestation of the human nature component of self-actualization Significant differences were found between ($H=13.215$; $p\leq 0.001$). This can be explained by the fact that in individuals of different periods, such positive qualities as sincere and positive interpersonal relationships, benevolence towards people, as well as trust in members of society, impartiality, neutrality and goodness are more pronounced in adulthood than in early adolescence and adolescence. Thus, individuals in adulthood pay more attention to the problems of other people and strive to have a positive attitude. The differences in research results among individuals of different ages can be interpreted as the fact that people in adulthood face life problems more often than people at earlier stages of psychological development, and as a result of feeling the support of others in such difficult situations, they understand the importance of helping others in similar difficult situations that have happened to them, and they approach them with empathy.

When comparing the results of individuals of different age groups in terms of the manifestation of cognitive needs, significant differences were noted between them. ($H=7.918$; $p\leq 0.05$). These indicators mean that the level of aspiration for new knowledge and information in individuals of different ages differs from each other, and psychological characteristics such as self-understanding, constant readiness for new impressions, interest in new things that are not directly related to satisfying any need, and thirst for uniqueness occur more often in people of adulthood than in members of the other two periods involved in the study. It can be seen that as a person ages, the ability to assimilate new information and try to know the factors that ensure the well-being of his life improves. It is possible that adults have higher scores on this scale because they are more likely to have a more disciplined approach to learning, have more patience, and are more likely to regularly monitor media than adolescents.

The pursuit of creativity, an important component of self-actualization in individuals during early adolescence, adolescence, and adulthood Significant differences were observed across age groups ($H=13.405$; $p\leq 0.001$). These indicators mean that characteristics such as a creative attitude towards life, a creative approach to activity, and a strong focus on unique aspects are formed to a higher degree in adolescent boys and girls than in people in early adolescence and adulthood. It should be noted that the high level of creativity among adolescents may be due to a number of factors, including their tendency to quickly master scientific and technological achievements, the high need to find their place in society by putting forward original ideas, and, given that the majority of individuals in this period are students, their skills in completing independent educational tasks in higher education institutions.

When comparing the results of self-awareness in individuals of different ages, significant differences were found between these values ($H=7.813$; $p\leq 0.05$). The results show that the levels of sensitivity to one's own desires and needs differ across the stages of human life, with higher levels recorded in individuals in adulthood than in the other two ontogenetic stages. Thus, it is clear that in individuals in adulthood, the full understanding of the qualities that characterize their personal essence, the invariance of their own views and assessments with external social norms are highly manifested. This expression of results may be due to the fact that in individuals at the stage of maturity, the abundance of life experience, the ability to distinguish internal psychological characteristics that caused unsuccessful situations, and the level of desire not to repeat them, prepare the ground for the realization of new individual qualities.

Conclusion. Based on the identified indicators, it should be noted that, according to the results of the study, significant differences were found in the components of self-actualization in individuals of different ages. In particular, individuals in adulthood have a higher level of self-actualization compared to people in early adolescence and adolescence. This difference can be seen in the characteristics of time planning, human nature, cognitive needs, and self-awareness.

In addition, it was found that the components of self-actualization, values, and striving for creativity, were better formed in people in adolescence .

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